

Local Wisdom Discourse in Disaster Mitigation of Mount Agung Eruption in Indonesian Literature

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Abstract

This research aims to identify local wisdom in natural disaster mitigation described in the novel entitled *Under the Eruption of Mount Agung* by Djelantik Santha. This novel is the only Indonesian literary work that tells the mitigation of the 1963 eruption of Mount Agung in Karangasem Regency, Bali, Indonesia. The data in this study were collected through reading, note-taking, and hermeneutic (interpretation) dialectical techniques. The collected data is then reduced and analyzed qualitatively using the sociology of literature and the theory of semiotics. The analysis found that the novel contains local Balinese wisdom, especially the local wisdom of the people of Selat Village, Karangasem Regency, Bali Province, regarding techniques for saving victims of the Mount Agung natural disaster. Local wisdom is depicted in the novel, such as togetherness and cooperation system, *yadnya* ceremony, *megibung* tradition, and *Kukul*. This local wisdom has played a major role in minimizing the victims of the Mount Agung natural disaster in the past.

Keywords: local wisdom discourse, Indonesian literature, disaster mitigation, Mount Agung eruption

INTRODUCTION

Every books or literary works have a message or valuable lesson. This statement is based on the assumption that literary works are the creation of authors as individuals and as social beings. Authors, in this context, have messages and ideas to share with the readers based on their personal experiences or the results of interactions with the social environment. In this reality, literary works depict life as a social reality (Damono, 1978, p.1). A literary work is created from the social reality faced by the authors. Of course, it is processed based on the ability of imagination and knowledge. Thus, a literary work has a relationship with society directly or indirectly (Routh and Wolff 1977, p. 18). Therefore, literary works in the form of stories can build a global way of thinking and form a multicultural view (Drake 2002, 2). The power of messages in inspiring literary works can move readers to take certain actions (Zak, 2015, p. 2–9).

In this research, the discourse of local wisdom in mitigating the natural disaster is found in the novel "*Di bawah Letusan Gunung Agung*" (hereafter *Under the Eruption of Mount Agung*) by Djentik Santha (2015), which was created based on the imagination, reflections, experiences, facts, and personal ideas and also as a result of interactions with the social environment. Especially this novel, as one of Indonesian literature, contains the discourse of local wisdom in mitigating the eruption of Mount Agung. That is why this novel was used as the primary data of this research.

Research on a discourse of local wisdom in mitigating the Mount Agung disaster is important. In fact, various Balinese local wisdom can be applied to minimize casualties during the eruption of Mount Agung. In this case, local wisdom derived from indigenous knowledge from the local community has proven to be important in reducing disaster risk (Dube & Munsaka, 2018; Iloka, 2016; Rai & Khawas, 2019; Ali et al., 2021). Various Balinese local wisdom is expressed in the novel, which needs to be understood and appreciated by the community and government, especially in disaster-affected areas. In dealing with natural disasters, the government often ignores local wisdom possessed by disaster-affected communities in minimizing disaster victims. The local wisdom is related to the togetherness and cooperation system adopted by the people in the Karangasem area. The government, in mitigating natural disasters, especially the eruption of Mount Agung, is based on something other than the local wisdom of the local community. The valuable lesson found in this

novel can be an input for the government in mitigating natural disasters, especially the natural disaster of the eruption of Mount Agung in the future.

Based on the above background, the main point discussed in this study is to examine the form of local wisdom discourse in mitigating the Mount Agung disaster in the novel *Under the Eruption of Mount Agung* and figure out the author's purpose of local wisdom discourse. Through this research, all parties, especially the Indonesian government, can learn from this data analysis related to management disasters. In addition, the sociology of literature and semiotic theory were used to discuss the discourse of local wisdom in the disaster mitigation of Mount Agung in the novel *Under the Eruption of Mount Agung* by Djelantik Santha. Then, the semiotic theory examined local wisdom discourse and its meaning. With these theories, the specified problems are expected to be solved and produce valid and scientifically justifiable research.

RESEARCH METHOD

The research is a literature study. The method used is qualitative data. This method emphasizes the quality of the data, not the quantity, using a literature study and reading, listening, note-taking, and hermeneutic (interpretation) dialectical techniques. The novel *Di bawah Letusan Gunung Agung* [Under the Eruption of Mount Agung] by Djelantik Shanta is read repeatedly to find data about the discourse of local wisdom in it. This novel was published by the Bali Provincial Language Center in 2015. The content of this novel consists of two parts and consists of 208 pages. The first part, from chapter I to IV, from page 1 to page 130, contains a love story between Sardula (the main character) and Ginanti (the second character), which does not tell about the Mount Agung eruption. The second part, chapters V to VI, from page 131 to page 208, contains stories about the struggle of the people of Selat village, Selat sub-district, Karangasem regency, Bali, in dealing with the eruption of Mount Agung, which occurred in 1963. Therefore, in this study, the data is focused on the second part. However, without ignoring the novel's first part, it particularly discusses the discourse of local wisdom in mitigating the Mount Agung eruption. Then, data reduction was carried out to find valid data. After that, the data was analyzed using a theory defined holistically or simultaneously. Finally, the analysis results are displayed in the form of narrative text.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

The terms of mitigation and local wisdom discourse would be discussed first. Mitigation is an action to reduce the impact of a disaster (Gougelet, 2016; Bullock et al., 2013; Ayuningtyas et al., 2021). Local wisdom shows how people behave and act in response to changes in the physical and cultural environment (Istiawati, 2016, p. 5). Local wisdom distinguishes certain groups' characteristics from others (Ratna, 2018, p. 365). Thus, this study aims to find the characteristics, attitudes, and actions of the Balinese people in dealing with natural disasters that are different from other communities in Indonesia, which are used to reduce the impact of the 1963 eruption of Mount Agung.

The novel "Under the Eruption of Mount Agung" by Djelantik Santha tells about the eruption of Mount Agung in 1963 as a fact. The incident of the eruption of Mount Agung was mixed with a fictional event in the form of a love story between Sardula and Ginanti. From the title, this novel suggests there is a message from the author to the reader that behind the eruption of Mount Agung, there are stories and events of fact and fiction that are taking place. Facts are events, quality of relationships, circumstances that happened or "existed," and situations or circumstances that have occurred (Susanto, 2015, p. 237). Therefore, the story in this novel is a combination between fact and fiction. Readers should be able to find ideas and ideas conveyed by the author behind the eruption of Mount Agung, the biggest natural disaster that has ever occurred in Bali.

Furthermore, facts are the realm of the human mind closely related to behaviorism or behavior (Kleden, 1998, p. 14). Fiction is a general term for created stories (Baldick, 1990, p. 83). The existence of fictional stories is believed to reflect something that has happened and predict what might happen in the future (Bina et al., 2017, p. 5). Therefore, fact and fiction cannot be separated in the creative world and the real world because there is fiction, and there is a fact in fiction. In the fact or reality of human life, there is often a world of fiction, and in the world of fiction, especially literary works, there is a world of facts, namely imaginary facts. Fiction is used inclusively for any literary narrative, whether in prose or made-up poetry, and not as historical truth (Abrams & Harpham, 2015, p. 61). Therefore, the novel *Under the Eruption of Mount Agung* by Djelantik Santha is positioned as a literary work that blends fiction and fact.

In the novel, the author conveys many discourses on local wisdom in mitigating the Mount Agung disaster in 1963. The natural disaster coincided with the Dewa *Yadnya* ceremony, a ceremony to worship the Almighty God, the largest at Besakih Temple, called the Eka Dasa Rudra ceremony, held once every hundred years. Dewa *Yadnya* is a form of Panca *Yadnya*, i.e., the five types of holy sacrifice that Balinese Hindus embrace. The Panca *Yadnya* are five sacred sacrifices that must be carried out to gain inner and outer safety. The concept of Panca *Yadnya* is required for Hindus to have a reciprocal relationship between nature and humans. Human life depends on natural conditions (Fedele et al., 2021, p. 3). For Hindus in Bali, nature also supports carrying out all kinds of rituals and traditions. On the other hand, nature also requires the role of humans who always maintain and are aware of their actions to always care for and preserve nature (Nguyen, 2019; Indahri, 2017; Yusuf & Azisi, 2020). Fostering good relationships between fellow humans and nature will create a comfortable environment and a better quality of life (Torres-Soto et al., 2022).

In addition, the Eka Dasa Rudra ceremony also coincides with the Galungan holiday, which is held every six months in Bali and Ngusabe Dalem in Selat Village. This situation becomes interesting for the author to describe the Dewa *Yadnya* ceremony in Bali in a situation where a natural disaster is occurring in the form of the eruption of Mount Agung. The author conveys various discourses of local wisdom to mitigate natural disasters during the Dewa *Yadnya* ceremony in Bali. Find the meaning or ‘signifier’ of local wisdom by interpreting the existing ‘signified’ through the semiotic theory of Ferdinand de Saussure. The sociology theory of literature from Diana Laurenson Alan Swingewood was used to find the sociological meaning in the local wisdom. In the analysis, the two theories are applied together holistically. Various discourses of local wisdom in the novel Under the Eruption of Mount Agung by Djelantik Santha are described as follows.

Togetherness and Cooperation System: Gotong Royong

Local wisdom in the form of “*gotong royong*” [togetherness and cooperation system] is the breath of Balinese life, although this local wisdom is decreasing, especially in urban areas. Togetherness and cooperation system in Balinese terms is *sagilik saguluk salunglung sabayantaka*, which seems to be explored by Djelantik Santha in the novel Under the Eruption of Mount Agung. It can be understood because this novel is set in 1963 when Balinese local wisdom was still strongly held by the Balinese in social interaction with their environment. Balinese people always sincerely help each other achieve common goals without expecting anything in return. It is the essence of the Balinese people’s togetherness and cooperation system. In the novel Under the Eruption of Mount Agung, the author explores much local Balinese wisdom in establishing a romance between Sardula and Ginanti. The discourse on Balinese local wisdom that the author widely expresses is the togetherness and cooperation system in dealing with the eruption of Mount Agung in 1963. It is understandable because this novel has a background story about natural disasters and Dewa *Yadnya* ceremonies which require a togetherness and cooperation system for togetherness, namely safety. The discourse of local wisdom in the form of the togetherness and cooperation system described by the author in his novel is through Sardula’s hard work with scouts and youth organizations in her village in accommodating refugees due to the eruption of Mount Agung. It can be seen in the following sentences as a signifier.

Data 1

Sardula gathered the Boy Scouts in the post, totaling 16 raisers and coaches. After discussion, the Scout group and two members of the village Security Organization served in Banjar Paruman while the village Security Organization group plus 3 Scouts served at the post. From the previous picket records, data on the number of refugees in Paruman amounted to 182 people. Therefore, Sardula ordered his men to take 100 kg of rice or one sack. Equipment and other materials are readily available there. So they started to divide the tasks into four groups.

Group I cooks, group II takes water, group III services, and group IV safety and raw material supply. Without further orders, they went straight to work (p. 143).

Sociologically, the sentences above proved that the Scout group and Youth Organizations in Selat Village took the initiative to help the needs of refugees from other villages who came from the base of Mount Agung, which was done in a cooperation system or *ngayah*. In Balinese, *ngayah* is used to help each other make offerings and equipment for a ceremony, especially the Dewa *Yadnya* ceremony at the temple.

Togetherness and cooperation systems existed long ago, and it has been Balinese life patterns. However, the cooperation system is decreasing because of changes in people's attitudes toward choosing individual life. Nevertheless, *ngayah* activity is still maintained, especially those related to *Dewa Yadnya* and the spiritual life of the Balinese people. *Ngayah* is a Balinese social obligation as the application of the concept of karma marga, carried out mutually, helping each other with a sincere heart, both in banjars and in temples. The *ngayah* system applies to Balinese people when preparing the offerings for ceremonies, especially in the *Dewa Yadnya* ceremony (see Figures 1 and 2). The time *ngayah* activities are carried out according to the community's agreement without sacrificing other socio-economic family activities. *Ngayah* is like "oxygen" that cannot be separated from various Hindu religious activities, an essential need that revives the religiosity of Hindu society (Pitriani, 2020, p. 159).

Figure 1 *Ngayah* (Females)

Figure 2 *Ngayah* (Males)

By using a simple style of language and a heroic atmosphere, the author has succeeded in describing the reader's inner mood when reading the signs above. In social psychology, the social environment of the people in Selat Village is the primary social environment because of the close relationship between individuals (Walgito 1991, 27). The youths and communities in Selat Village, under Sardula's command, fought hard to help each other mitigate and assist in handling the needs of refugees to minimize casualties. In this mitigation, the author showed other local Balinese wisdom, namely coffee, tea, or mineral from pieces of bamboo called *bumbung* and food wrappers from banana leaves called *tekor*. It can be seen from the following sentences as a signifier.

Data 2

Many refugees, especially those who brought small children, were exhausted. Some even cry from hunger. Sardula, who went around seeing the situation of the refugees, was very sad. For a while, he ordered to provide sweet tea for the children and coffee for the elderly and adults. Due to a shortage of glasses, Sardula looked for bamboo and cut it into pieces as a substitute for drinking glasses.

Once the rice was cooked, it was immediately distributed by Group III, which was in charge of providing services to refugees. They lined up to take their share of rice, vegetables, and salted fish. Those who did not eat salted fish were given a piece of omelet and vegetables. They used iron plates and banana leaves for cutlery, and some used baskets, pans, or basket lids covered with makeshift leaves. As the night progressed, more and more refugees came. Sardula asked for two more sacks of rice. The supply of side dishes was very lacking. Although there was enough seasoning, salt, shrimp paste, chili, salted fish, and peanuts were all gone. Even the refugees themselves participated in giving up their chickens voluntarily for a side dish to be eaten together (pp. 143-144)

The sentences above show sociologically that the people of Selat Village have social sensitivity or emphatic. In facing the eruption of Mount Agung, the community helps each other so that the loss of life and material can be minimized. Balinese local wisdom like this should be a model for mitigation in other areas when facing natural disasters. So far, only the government has worked hard to mitigate natural disasters because the government is seen as responsible for its people's safety.

In a disaster emergency, the community should not depend on conventional tools to mitigate; any tool can be used for mutual safety. The local Balinese wisdom described in the above sentences is about a tool for drinking coffee called *bumbung* and a utensil for eating rice from banana leaves called *tekor*. Until now,

Balinese people, especially in rural areas, still use *bumbung* for drinking coffee and *tekor* for eating. *Bumbung* and *tekor* are considered more sacred than glasses and plates.

Yadnya Ceremony

Another Balinese local wisdom is also found in the novel, which the author expresses is the *Dewa Yadnya* ceremony. The *Dewa Yadnya* ceremony is a sacred sacrifice addressed to God. *Dewa Yadnya*, as Balinese local wisdom, is usually performed by cooperation or the *ngayah* system. *Yadnya* is a holy sacrifice on the condition that: (1) the *yadnya* is based on sincere sincerity with a pure heart, and it cannot be forced; (2) *yadnya* is based on love that is manifested with a sincere sense of devotion, love for fellow humans, love for animals and plants, and love for the surrounding environment; (3) *yadnya* based on ability; and (4) *yadnya* based on obligations because it has been blessed in life (Setyaningsih 2020; M. Yusuf and Azisi 2020). The Hindu community performs *yadnya* activities almost daily, ranging from small ceremonies to large ceremonies held at certain times (Dharmawan 2020). By doing *yadnya*, the Hindu community in Bali believes that this world will be balanced to create peace (Utari and Subagia 2021). There are five types of *yadnya* performed by the Hindu community in Bali namely: (1) *Dewa Yadnya*, namely sacred sacrifices before God Almighty; (2) *Pitra Yadnya*, namely sacred sacrifices to ancestors; (3) *Rsi Yadnya*, namely holy sacrifices to the priests; (4) *Manusa Yadnya*, namely holy sacrifices to fellow human beings; and (5) *Butha Yadnya*, which is a sacred sacrifice to the environment of the universe (Widari and Sutama 2021).

It can be seen from the main background of the novel is the eruption of Mount Agung in 1963, the *Eka Dasa Rudra ceremony*, which is held once every 100 years at Besakih temple, *Galungan* holiday, and *Ngusabe Dalem* in Selat Village. Therefore, it can be understood that *Dewa Yadnya's* local wisdom, togetherness, and cooperation system or *ngayah* are dominant in the love story between Sardula and Ginatri.

Figure 3 Eruption of Mount Agung

Conducting *yadnya* ceremonies, especially *Dewa Yadnya* ceremonies such as the *Eka Dasa Rudra* ceremony during the eruption of Mount Agung, caused various views or perspectives in Hindu society in Bali. The following sentences are evidence found in the novel.

Data 3

There is a positive perspective; namely, there is an understanding and belief that God accepts the Taur Agung Eka Dasa Rudra ceremony with a sign of natural greatness preceded or accompanied by earthquake vibrations, strong winds, volcanic eruptions, and others.

A negative perception questions why God or nature shows his anger to accept this great *yadnya* ceremony. There is probably an error in the implementation of this work in the ceremonial facilities, or the timing of its implementation is not right. Because the work of Eka Dasa Rudra should be held during the year, Caka rah windu tenggek windu or tens, and the year unit is numbered 0. Meanwhile, this time it was held in the year Caka1885.

There is also a moderate perception, assuming Mount Agung has not erupted for too long. It is just a coincidence that this 1963 eruption coincided with the work of Eka Dasa Rudra. Whereas in 1952, a German scientist climbed Mount Agung and had time to stay at SR No. 1 Selat. He said Mount Agung would erupt about 10 years from then (pp.131-132).

The sentences above can be interpreted as a sign that the belief of the Hindu community in Bali towards the purpose of holding a *yadnya* ceremony has dynamics. Sociologically, Balinese people have a dynamic view

of reading natural signs when a yadnya ceremony is held. It depends on the experience and knowledge of each individual about the meaning of a yadnya. Some think irrationally, some are rational, some think positively, and some think negatively and moderately, but the yadnya ceremony is carried out sincerely. This mindset still exists today in Bali's dynamics of Hindu community life. Djelantik Santha seems to have succeeded in capturing and expressing the reality and thought patterns that develop in a society by using a language style that readers easily understand. The author may also have made observations or research on the mindset of the Hindu community in Bali about the meaning of a yadnya. Indirectly, the author also subtly conveys social criticism so that the Hindu community in Bali has mulat sasira or self-introspection in performing yadnya ceremonies.

When Mount Agung erupted, three Dewa Yadnya ceremonies were held in the disaster area: Taur Agung Eka Dasa Rudra held at Besakih temple, Galungan holiday, and Ngusabe Dalem in Selat Village. Even though a very dangerous natural disaster is happening, the three Dewa Yadnya ceremonies can be carried out, but are carried out. The Ngusabe Dalem ceremony in Selat Village is usually held lively, but because of a natural disaster, it is held, as shown in the novel with the following data.

Data 4

Unfortunately, due to the influx of refugees, the Ngusabe Sri ceremony at the Dalem Selat temple, which is usually lively, was only attended by the stakeholders and officers of the Selat Traditional Village, as well as the people who were near the temple (p.147).

In addition to the *Ngusabe* ceremony at the Dalem Temple, Selat Village is close to a major Hindu holiday, Galungan Day. Galungan is celebrated by Hindus to celebrate the victory of dharma against adharma or the victory of good over evil, and is celebrated every six months according to the Balinese calendar. People affected by the natural disaster of Mount Agung continue to celebrate the holiday, although in a simple way. Sociologically, this is an awareness of the religiosity of the Hindu community in Bali, which is a force in maintaining Balinese religious, customary, and cultural life.

Data 5

On the day of Galungan, March 20, 1963, early in the morning, Ginanti's mother and sister had gone to the general hospital to see Sardula while bringing offerings to be offered at the hospital temple. They find Ginanti making coffee and Sardula having breakfast.

"Yanti, what are you doing? Has de Sardula showered yet? This is my mother bringing offerings for the rules at the temple. I wish Sardula a speedy recovery," said her mother approaching them.

"I'm making coffee while accompanying brother Sar while having breakfast," Ginanti said cheerfully, then accepted her mother's offer. Yanti put down her coffee, put on a scarf, and went to Padmasana to deliver offerings. Don't forget to ask for holy water (Tirta) for Sardula. His mother and sister chatted very well with him. Sardula also showed her wounds were getting better. After giving water to Sardula and finishing her coffee, Yanti got ready to go home. The fruits and snacks, rice with side dishes used for offerings, were left for Sardula. Many people also came on the day of Galungan (pp.167-168).

The Balinese Hindu community strongly believes in the function and meaning of a yadnya in a religious holiday. By offering yadnya in the form of offerings (see Figure 4) and asking for Tirta (holy water) (see Figure 5), it is hoped that all requests to God will be granted. It can be seen in Sardula's family, who always remember God and asks for healing on the *Galungan* holiday for Sardula, whose feet were hit by hot lava while helping victims of the eruption of Mount Agung. By describing the situation where the patient is being treated in a hospital in real terms and simple language, the author has succeeded in bringing the atmosphere of the reader to the will desired by the author.

Figure 4 Offering

Figure 5 Metirte

The big Yadnya ceremony when Mount Agung erupted in 1963 was the *Taur Agung Eka Dasa Rudra* ceremony (see Figure 6). This big ceremony was held at Besakih temple, the largest temple in Bali and located at the base of Mount Agung. This ceremony is held once every 100 years. The *Yadnya Eka Dasa Rudra* ceremony is a worship ceremony for the 11 Kala Rudra, which controls all directions of the wind. This Hindu ceremony is celebrated only once every 100 years, resulting in the number 0 (zero). This ceremony is held to welcome the calculation of the rotation of the Saka year when the units and tens start to become number one. According to Rudra Tattwa, this ceremony is carried out so that the universe (Bhuana Agung) and humans (Bhuana Alit) are in harmony (Adji 2008; Asmarani 2020).

Figure 6 Eka Dasa Rudra Yadnya Ceremony in 1963

Apart from the three perspectives of the Balinese people's views on holding a yadnya ceremony, as described above, the Balinese people strongly believe that under any circumstances, the yadnya ceremony must be carried out when the time is right. For the Hindu community in Bali, the yadnya ceremony is a spiritual effort so that the peace and prosperity of the community are realized and disasters can end. In his novel, the author has succeeded in describing the socio-religious condition of the Balinese people in the atmosphere of natural disasters so that the reader can also understand the socio-cultural of the Hindu community in Bali.

Tradition of Megibung (Eating Together)

Another Balinese local wisdom in mitigating the natural disaster of Mount Agung erupting is the *megibung* tradition. This tradition is still maintained in the socio-cultural life of the Hindu community in Bali until now. *Megibung* tradition contains noble values, such as togetherness, equality, social solidarity, aesthetics, effectiveness, and an arena for social communication. The value of togetherness can be seen in the *megibung* tradition, where several people eat together in one place. The value of equality can be seen in people who are *megibung* because they do not take into account social status. The value of social solidarity can be seen when people get up, give, and take each other. The aesthetic value can be seen in the *megibung* process. Some ethics must be obeyed, for example, following the signal to start eating and following the *megibung* procedure orderly. The value of effectiveness can be seen in the *megibung* tradition, which does not require a lot of places to eat, and the time is more efficient. In the *megibung* tradition, you can also use a forum to communicate between *megibung* participants.

There are so many values in the *Megibung* tradition, so this tradition needs to be carried out in social life, especially in mitigating natural disasters. *Megibung* is a tradition of eating together in one dish by sitting in a circular position with eight people (Kasih et al., 2019, p. 103–9). The uniqueness of the *megibung* tradition is that men *megibung* with men. In contrast, the women are together with women. *Megibung* participants do not have to be with people known to each other. The guests who did not know each other sat and ate together. The dish eaten together is called *gibungan*, which consists of rounded rice and is served on a tray. *Gibungan* is equipped with various types of Balinese dishes made from pork.

In its development, the current *megibung* tradition no longer uses *dulang* (see Figure 7) as a dish or place for food. Kasih et al. (2019) mentioned that sometimes men and women are not separated, but in a dish or other place as long as it can contain all the food to be eaten together and there is mixing between men and women. At this time, the *dulang* for the Hindu community in Bali was only used as a place for offerings or to eat for priests or people who were purified.

Figure 7 Dulang

In *megibung* tradition, male and female participants are separated and sometimes mixed according to the situation and conditions. It happens because it involves aesthetic values and modesty, not because of gender discrimination. Usually, the men eat more and take longer to eat, so they must be separated because when they finish eating, no one should precede getting up from their seats.

In Bali, the *megibung* tradition is not only practiced by the Balinese Hindu community. However, it is also commonly practiced by the Muslim community in Kepawon Denpasar Village, Singaraja Pegayaman Village, Karangasem Kecicang Village, and other Muslim communities. They carry out the *megibung* tradition because it has been their cultural heritage for generations and is carried out during religious events in these areas.

In the novel *Under the Eruption of Mount Agung*, Djelantik Santha describes the *megibung* tradition, when Sardula and members of the scouts prepare food for refugees who have just arrived at the refugee camp. Sardula, scout members, and the community worked hand in hand to prepare food for the refugees. Regional officials who had visited the refugee camp were very proud and appreciated the community's hard work in helping prepare food and drinks under Sardula's command. The author describes this situation and the *megibung* tradition as follows.

Data 6

At almost 11.00 pm, the last refugee arrived and was escorted by the police and the village head. As many as 23 people were very tired. They are prepared to eat with *megibung* (eat together) utensils in the banjar in 4 seles (groups). They ate voraciously because of hunger and thirst through the cliff, the abyss in pitch darkness, step by step. Thank goodness they still made it here. The officers who have not eaten are also prepared to eat all of them with simple side dishes. There are still two chickens that must be cut, fried, and just sliced (p. 144).

In the *megibung* tradition, men and women are divided into several groups. Initially, each group of participants must be odd, five or seven people and one person as the leader who regulates the course of *megibung*. It reflects the principle of democracy, but the number of participants in each election is no longer

determined due to socio-cultural developments. The data above also mentions one of the traditional foods served to refugees: fried or grilled chicken with spices.

Data 6 above can be interpreted as a sign that in a panic situation due to a disaster, Sardula and the community help each other to prepare food for the refugees. The values of social solidarity and community solidarity are reflected in the hard work of the volunteers in helping the refugees. Using simple word choices, readers can imagine the situation that occurred at that time. The author also describes the situation of the *megibung* tradition as follows.

Data 7

“Brother Scouts, since all the guests have eaten, it’s your turn to eat. After that, we will continue the task of cleaning this equipment. Who knows, tomorrow it will be used again,” said Sardula, telling his men to eat.

That’s how they ate together and finished the vegetables and fried chicken, which had quite a spicy seasoning. Unexpectedly, the commander appeared, and the father of Sri and Sukanti smiled, seeing the children eating.

“Good evening, commander. How about joining us in *megibung*?”

“I’m fine, Sardula. I just came home from eating, but a cup of coffee might be good.”

“Okay, sir, there is fried cassava,” said Sri, immediately making 2 cups of coffee for her father and the sub-district head who had also come to see the refugees. “Aah, Sri, if you are eating *megibung*, you can’t go down. You can make it too. As long as you tell me where the coffee and sugar are,” said the commander smiling (pp.144-145).

Data 7 above can be interpreted as a sign that the togetherness and solidarity of the community and local officials are very good. Togetherness and solidarity are needed when facing a natural disaster to minimize disaster victims. The *megibung* tradition in mitigating natural disasters is important because this tradition contains the values of the socio-cultural life of the Indonesian people, as described above. In the data above, there are also ethical and aesthetic values in the *megibung* tradition, namely that when people are *megibung*, other participants are not allowed to get up or stand to take something because there are officers who will take it. In addition, the *megibung* tradition does not require many eating utensils. It can provide enthusiasm for life and motivation for people facing a disaster.

Kulkul

Kulkul is a traditional communication tool for Balinese people, especially Hindus. *Kulkul* is usually made of wood or bamboo (see Figure 9). *Kulkuls* made of wood are usually used for temples or banjars, while *Kulkuls* made of bamboo are usually for games or for community groups that are small and simple and do not have a special place, such as in a temple or banjar. *Kulkul* is one of the communication tools for traditional Balinese organizations, such as traditional villages, traditional banjars, subak, and various sekaa (Windia 2014, 242). The *Kulkul* is placed in a special place known as the bale. *Kulkul* is generally used or placed in bale banjars and temples. Banjar is where Balinese people meet to discuss an issue, while temples are sacred places for Hindus. The building where the *Kulkul* is in the temple or banjar is called Balai *Kulkul*. The sound of the *Kulkul* depends on the pattern of beatings carried out by a special officer. Each *Kulkul* beating pattern has a different meaning.

Balinese, especially Hindus, are very familiar with every *Kulkul* sound pattern and its meaning, which has been agreed upon indirectly and from generation to generation. The Balinese Hindu community knows what to do when they hear the sound of a *Kulkul* with a certain pattern of strokes. Balinese people are very obedient to the sound of the *Kulkul* because they will be subject to social sanctions if they do not comply. This social sanction is what the Balinese Hindu community fears. The *Kulkul* is beaten if there are *ngayah* activities and a series of piodalan at the temple or banjar, meetings or sangkep, the death of a member of the banjar, fires, fights, natural disasters, and other urgent circumstances. Therefore, the sound of *Kulkul* is divided into three: tri brata sandining *Kulkul*, namely: dharma, precepts, and sesana. Dharma means that the *Kulkul* is voiced to carry out religious ceremonies according to the teachings of Hinduism. Sila, namely *Kulkul*, for social purposes, such as helping each other. Sesana, which means *Kulkul*, is voiced for humanitarian purposes,

such as providing help when needed, for example, during natural disasters, fires, thefts, and so on (Windia, 2014, p. 242).

Figure 8 (a) *Kukul* at the Temple, (b) *Kukul* at *Bale Banjar* (Community meeting hall), (c) *Kukul* Made of Bamboo

There are various patterns of beating the *Kukul*, depending on the need and purpose of beating the *Kukul*. The *Kukul* in the temple, or *bale banjar*, should not be beaten by people carelessly but by a person with a special duty for that, called *sinoman*. *Sinoman* officers are usually appointed in turn by the *kelian* temple or *banjar*. There are three types of *Kukul* beats or knocks, namely: *Kukul* deliberations, which are intended to provide information about meetings for village deliberations; knocking on the death knuckle to notify the village community that a member of the community's family has died; and the tap of *Kukul* *pancabaya* or called *Kukul* *bulus* which serves to inform the village community that a natural disaster, riot, crime has occurred in the village (Sudipa & Denanjaya, 2020, p.108). *Kukul* punches to provide information, and *Kukul* punches to inform death, usually one-on-one blows quickly, slowly, and ends with another fast punch. *Kukul* *Bulus* was hit quickly from beginning to end due to a disaster.

In the novel *Under the Eruption of Mount Agung*, local wisdom in the form of the sound of the *Kukul* *bulus* helps a lot in mitigating the natural disasters of Mount Agung, especially the one that occurred in 1963, to minimize human casualties. The sound of the *Kukul* *bulus* is used to warn the people in Selat Village about the occurrence of a natural disaster. The people of Selat Village who are experiencing a disaster are very obedient to the sound of the *Kukul* being beaten by the officers, not by the *sinoman* because it is an emergency in a disaster situation. The author describes this in the state and situation of the people who panic because there are bursts of lava and hot clouds from the top of Mount Agung.

Data 8

Finally, Sardula immediately ordered her mother and sister out of the house to the east. Before he had time to think about hitting the village *Kukul* in the Great Hall, suddenly sulfurous smoke covered the entire village. The situation turned pitch black. Visibility is not more than two meters. Only the cries, calls, and screams of people looking for their families could be heard here and there. In a situation like this, it appears humans are very selfish and individualistic. Sardula covered her nose with a cloth. He went to the post, deserted. Only one person was passing at the crossroads to the north.

“Hey, who’s that? Please ring the village *Kukul*, *Kukul* *bulus*,” shouted Sardula. Some scouts came to the post. Sardula distributed the rest of the pieces that were left to her. The *Kukul* *bulus* can also be heard even though it is mixed with the sound of stones colliding in the Lagon river. Pak Sakiban and Pak Gomboh (police) were busy running here and there, ordering the residents to evacuate to the east. The Lagon River in the west has been covered by hot lava. Sardula returned to the east to see her mother and sister at the schools and hotels used as temporary shelters. After meeting and leaving his bag there, he returned to the village looking for the others. He has not found Ginanti and his family (pp. 155-156).

Data 8 above showed that the signs are a chaotic and panicked situation in the face of the eruption of Mount Agung. The community can still be united in evacuations by communicating the sound of the *Kukul* *bulus*. By using a simple language style and describing a tense situation, the author succeeded in influencing the reader's feelings to enter and melt into the tense situation described by the author. Another sign

shows that a leader always thinks about the interests and safety of society and others compared to his safety and interests, as Sardula points out. The cohesiveness and togetherness of leaders and the community are always reflected in the efforts to mitigate the Mount Agung disaster in this novel by Djelantik Santha. Balinese local wisdom in the form of the sound of *Kukul* (*Kukul bulus*) is also important in its presence in the social life of the Balinese Hindu community.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, several forms of Balinese local wisdom in mitigating the Mount Agung disaster were found, such as the togetherness and cooperation system, *yadnya* ceremony, *megibung* tradition, and *Kukul*. The Balinese local wisdom played an essential role in natural disaster mitigation efforts to minimize disaster victims, especially casualties, such as the incident in the novel *Under the Eruption of Mount Agung* by Djeantik Santha. The author describes Balinese local wisdom in mitigating the Mount Agung disaster by using a simple style of language and playing with the panic and chaos of the story during the eruption of Mount Agung.

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